

Kinetics and Mechanism of Electron Transfer Reactions in Fluoride-coordinated Bismuth(v) Complex : Oxidation of Phosphorous Acid in Aqueous HClO₄-HF Mixture

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Kinetics of oxidation of phosphorous acid with bismuth(v) fluoride complex have been studied in HClO₄-HF mixture. The reaction is first order with respect to each reactant and the second order rate constant at 45° was evaluated. The hydrogen ion dependence is complex. Free radicals are indicated in the reaction. The mode of electron transfer from the substrate to the oxidant has been indicated via a bridge outer-sphere mechanism. The enthalpy of activation for the hydrogen ion independent step and the entropy of activation were calculated. The rate of the reaction was found to be independent of sodium fluoride and HF concentrations.

THOUGH the oxidation of hypophosphorous acid with bismuth(v) in HClO₄-HF mixture has been reported¹, the solution chemistry of bismuth(v) is not well-explored. Therefore, kinetic studies of the title reaction were initiated. Furthermore, the comparative study of the title reaction with other reactions of phosphorous acid by metal ion oxidants^{2,3} will help in developing a reaction model.

Experimental

Disodium monohydrogen phosphite (Na₂HPO₃·5H₂O; AnalaR) was employed as a source of phosphorous acid. The preparation and standardisation of bismuth(v) solution in HClO₄-HF mixture were reported elsewhere¹. Other chemicals were of either AnalaR or guaranteed reagent grade.

Reaction of phosphorous acid and iodine in aqueous acidic solution is slow and does not interfere with the modified method⁴ for the iodometric analysis of bismuth(v).

In stoichiometric experiments, phosphorous acid was determined iodimetrically⁵. An aliquot (5 cm³) of the reaction mixture was neutralised to pH ~7 by the addition of NaOH solution, and a known volume of iodine solution was then added followed by ammonium borate. The resulting solution was kept for ~20 min, then acidified and titrated against thiosulphate in presence of EDTA using starch indicator. The first order rate constants were calculated in presence of large excess of H₃PO₃ over [Bi^v].

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: Bismuth(v) mixed with an excess of phosphorous acid in HClO₄-HF mixture was

kept at 45° for ~8 h and the excess phosphorous acid determined iodimetrically⁶. Complete reaction was ensured by absence of bismuth(v) tested with KI. The results (Table 1) indicate stoichiometry of the reaction as,

The higher ratios of $\Delta[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3]/\Delta[\text{Bi}^{\text{v}}]$ are ascribed to the self-decomposition of bismuth(v).

TABLE-1 STOICHIOMETRIC RESULTS OF OXIDATION OF PHOSPHOROUS ACID WITH BISMUTH(V) IN HClO₄-HF MIXTURE

[HClO ₄]=1.0 mol dm ⁻³ , [HF]=1.5 mol dm ⁻³ , Temp.=45°		
[Bi ^v] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[H ₃ PO ₃] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	$\frac{\Delta[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3]}{\Delta[\text{Bi}^{\text{v}}]}$
1.4	4.0	1.12
1.4	6.0	1.12
1.4	8.0	1.05
1.7	4.0	1.12
1.7	5.0	1.12
1.7	6.0	1.15
1.7	8.0	1.10
3.4	10.0	1.15
4.4	10.0	1.10
5.4	10.0	1.10

A plot of log Bi^v versus time at < 45° is curved downwards (Fig. 1) in presence or absence of bismuth(III) and/or phosphorous(v). The reaction was studied at an elevated temperature where such induction periods are absent and simple first order behaviour is ensured.

Kinetics: The pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*_{obs}) were found to be independent of the initial concentrations of bismuth(v) indicating a first-order dependence on bismuth(v) (Table 2). However, *k*_{obs} increases proportionately with [P^{III}] exhibiting first order kinetics with respect to [P^{III}]. The second

Fig. 1. Pseudo-first order plots, $[Bi^V]=1.3 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[H_3PO_3]=5.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[HF]=1.5$ mol dm^{-3} , $[HClO_4]=1.0$ mol dm^{-3} , temp. = 35° : (\otimes) $[Bi^{III}]=0.0$, $[PO_4^{3-}]=0.0$, (Δ) $[Bi^{III}]=0.01$ mol dm^{-3} , $[PO_4^{3-}]=0.0$, (\circ) $[Bi^{III}]=0.0$, $[PO_4^{3-}]=0.01$ mol dm^{-3} and (\square) $[Bi^V]=1.02 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[H_3PO_3]=5.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} ; $[HClO_4]$ 1.0 mol dm^{-3} , $[HF]=1.5$ mol dm^{-3} , $[PO_4^{3-}]=0.01$ mol dm^{-3} , temp. = 45° .

order rate constants were calculated from k_{obs} against $[P^{III}]$ plots. Polymerisation of methylmethacrylate (MMA) in the reaction mixture indicates formation of free radicals.

TABLE 2—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER (k_{obs}) AND SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k) FOR REACTION BETWEEN BISMUTH(V) AND H_3PO_3 IN $HClO_4$ -HF MIXTURES

$[HClO_4]=1.0$ mol dm^{-3} , $[HF]=1.5$ mol dm^{-3} , Temp. = 45°

$[Bi^V]$ $\times 10^5$ mol dm^{-3}	$[H_3PO_3]$ $\times 10^2$ mol dm^{-3}	k_{obs} $\times 10^4$ s^{-1}	k $\times 10^3$ $dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$
1.0	5.0	3.1	6.2
1.6	5.0	3.2	6.4
1.7	5.0	3.2	6.4
2.0	5.0	3.1	6.2
2.2	5.0	3.2	6.4
2.8	5.0	3.3	6.6
3.3	5.0	3.2	6.4
3.7	5.0	3.2	6.3
4.3	5.0	3.1	6.3
4.7	5.0	3.2	6.3
5.1	5.0	—	6.3 ^a
5.4	5.0	—	6.4 ^a
5.7	5.0	—	6.3 ^a
1.6	1.0	—	6.6 ^a
1.6	2.0	1.3	6.3
1.6	3.0	2.0	6.5
1.6	8.0	5.1	6.4
1.6	10.0	6.4	6.4
1.5	4.0	2.6	6.6
1.5	5.0	3.3	6.5
1.5	6.0	4.0	6.6
1.5	7.0	4.6	6.6
1.5	9.0	5.9	6.5
1.5	4.0	—	6.3
1.6	5.0	—	6.4
1.6	6.0	—	6.3

^aSecond order rate constants obtained from second order plots.

Hydrogen ion dependence: $[HClO_4]$ was varied from 0.5 to 2.0 mol dm^{-3} at $I=2.0$ mol dm^{-3} (adjusted with lithium perchlorate). The value of k increases with $[HClO_4]$ tending towards a limiting value at higher concentration of hydrogen ions (Fig. 2). Such a kinetic behaviour is in conformity with the empirical rate law (2),

$$-\frac{d[Bi^V]}{dt} = \frac{A+B[H^+]}{C+D[H^+]} [Bi^V]_T [H_3PO_3]_T \quad (2)$$

where, A , B , C and D are constants. k is independent of ionic strength (1.0–3.0 mol dm^{-3}), $[HF]$ (1.0–2.5 mol dm^{-3}) and $[NaF]$ (0.01–0.1 mol dm^{-3}). Since the rate is not affected by HF and F^- ions, any equilibrium involving Bi^V with HF and F^- ions is also ruled out and suggests that the highest fluoro species of bismuth(v), viz. BiF_6^- is the reactive species ($[Bi^V]_T \approx [BiF_6^-]$).

Fig. 2. Variation of hydrogen ion; $[Bi^V]=1.4 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[H_3PO_3]=5.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[HF]=1.6$ mol dm^{-3} , $[PO_4^{3-}]=1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} , $I=2.0$ mol dm^{-3} : (\circ) 45° , (Δ) 50° and (\square) 55° .

Mechanism: Since the rate is independent of HF and NaF , BiF_6^- appears to be the reaction species as has also been assumed in the reaction of Bi^V with H_3PO_3 in $HClO_4$ - HF mixture. Due to the non-absorbing nature of bismuth(v) in uv and visible region⁷, and the corrosive effects of HF on glass and metals, proper speciation of the fluoro-species of bismuth(v) is difficult.

The reported acid dissociation constant^{8,9} of H_3PO_3 (0.01 $dm^3 mol^{-1}$) at 25° is likely to be smaller⁹ at 45° and thus the phosphorous acid in presence of $[H^+]=1.0$ mol dm^{-3} will almost exclusively be in the molecular form. A probable reaction mechanism comprising steps (3) to (7) can, therefore,

be suggested.

The step (6) yields an highly reactive intermediate owing to the labilisation of P-H bond after proton attack on the P=O oxygen. The labilisation of P-H bond requires that all but one oxygen must be bound to proton or metal before proton attack can labilise P-H bond. Both anhydride formation and proton attack on the oxygen have also been considered to be the factors for labilisation of P-H bond in the oxidation of H_3PO_3 by chromium(vi)³.

The intermediate (I) permits a facile internal oxidation-reduction. The formation constant of the complex (I) should be small owing to the saturation of all coordination sites of bismuth(v).

Applying steady-state treatment ($d[I]/dt=0$), equation (8) is obtained,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Bi}^{\text{V}}]}{dt} = \left\{ \frac{k_1(k_3 + k_4K[\text{H}^+])}{k_2 + k_3 + k_4K[\text{H}^+]} \right\} [\text{Bi}^{\text{V}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3]_{\text{T}} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{or } k = \frac{k_1(k_3 + k_4K[\text{H}^+])}{k_2 + k_3 + k_4K[\text{H}^+]} \quad (9)$$

where, $[\text{Bi}^{\text{V}}]_{\text{T}}$ and $[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3]_{\text{T}}$ are the gross analytical concentrations of bismuth(v) ($\sim [\text{BiF}_6^-]$) and phosphorous acid respectively. k was calculated to be $(6.4 \pm 0.4) \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 45° . However, two limiting situations can be envisaged for the evaluation of the various rate constants from such a complicated rate law (9). Firstly, when $[\text{H}^+] = 0$, $k_4K[\text{H}^+] \ll (k_2 + k_3)$, the rate law (9) reduces to (10),

$$k = \frac{k_1k_3}{k_2 + k_3} \quad (10)$$

Secondly, $k_4K[\text{H}^+] \gg (k_2 + k_3)$ is valid for higher concentrations of hydrogen ion and that reduces the rate law (9) to (11),

$$k = k_1 \quad (11)$$

Thus equation (11) satisfies the condition of the rate being independent of hydrogen ion concentration when the latter is sufficiently high.

The values of $k_1k_3/(k_2 + k_3)$ to be $(3.8 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-3}$, $(7.6 \pm 0.4) \times 10^{-3}$ and $(14.0 \pm 0.7) \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and k_1 to be $(6.6 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-3}$, $(13.3 \pm 0.7) \times 10^{-3}$ and $(21.9 \pm 1.2) \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ were calculated in two limiting situations at $I=2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $45, 50$ and 55° respectively.

The polymerization of methyl methacrylate supports formation of free radicals in the title reaction. This is not unusual as the phosphite radicals are reportedly¹⁰ known to be formed in solutions. The phosphite radicals also subscribe to the formation of transient bismuth(iv), again not a unique proposition in view of well-established As^{IV} in solution⁹. Probably, it is the reason of slight induction period observed in the title reaction at low temperature. Moreover, reactions indicating free radicals also exhibit induction period. However, it is difficult to highlight the probable reasons of induction period with the available results.

The intermediate (I) with hydrogen bonding does not show much promise for internal oxidation-reduction. However, if I is considered to be the outer-sphere bridged intermediate(III), hydrogen bonding can assist in bringing bismuth(v) in close proximity of phosphorous(III) for facile transfer of the electron-pair from phosphorous to bismuth(v) in two successive steps of one electron each.

The energy and entropy of activation for k_1 path are (97 ± 6) kJ mol⁻¹ and (11 ± 2) JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ at 45° respectively. These activation parameters are not unusual in view of the involvement of free radicals though entropy of activation is more positive. Probably, it is the loosening of the bridged intermediate on participation of a proton in the transition state that increases the entropy.

Interestingly, similar pattern of reactivity for Tl^{III}-P(III) and Bi^V-P(III) reactions can be ascribed to the closer thermodynamic potentials of Tl^{III}/Tl^I and Bi^V/Bi^{III} couples. The faster oxidation of Bi^V-P(I) than Bi^V-P(III) is the usual kinetic trend observed almost in all oxidations of phosphorous acid with metal ion oxidants in solutions. Probably high energy barriers available in phosphite might be one such reason of low reactivity.

Appendix :

Let A and B be reactants and C and D the intermediates.

$$-\frac{d[A]}{dt} \text{ or } -\frac{d[B]}{dt} = C\{k_3 + k_4K[H^+]\} \quad (1)$$

Applying steady state treatment to intermediate [C],

$$0 = \frac{d[C]}{dt} = k_1[A][B] - k_2[C] - k_3[C] - k_4K[C][H^+]$$

$$[C] = \frac{k_1[A][B]}{k_2 + k_3 + k_4K[H^+]} \quad (2)$$

Substituting the value of [C] from equation (2) to equation (1),

$$-\frac{d[A]}{dt} = -\frac{d[B]}{dt} = \left\{ \frac{k_1(k_3 + k_4K[H^+])}{k_2 + k_3 + k_4K[H^+]} \right\} [A][B]$$

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